

Synthesis, spectroscopic characterization, thermal decomposition and antimicrobial studies of manganese(III), iron(III) and cobalt(III) complexes with Schiff base derived from thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde and 2-aminobenzoic acid

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Abstract : A Schiff base namely *N*-(2-thiophenyl methylene)-2-aminobenzoic acid (HNTA) has been prepared by condensation of thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde with 2-aminobenzoic acid in 1 : 1 molar ratio. Manganese(III), iron(III) and cobalt(III) complexes of this Schiff base have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, IR, UV-Vis, ¹H NMR, FAB mass, magnetic measurements, thermogravimetric analysis and XRD studies. The IR spectral data show that the ligand is coordinated to the metal ion in a tridentate manner with ONS donor sites of the carboxylate oxygen, azomethine nitrogen and thiophene ring sulphur atom. Magnetic moment measurements and electronic spectral data suggest a distorted octahedral geometry for manganese(III) complex and six-coordinated octahedral geometry for iron(III) and cobalt(III) complexes. Proton NMR spectral data reveal that the carboxylate proton displaced during complexation. The thermal decomposition studies of iron(III) complex show three stage decomposition and for each stage, kinetic parameters have been evaluated using Coats-Redfern equation. XRD patterns of the ligand and its cobalt(III) complex show orthorhombic crystal system. The ligand and the metal complexes are evaluated for antibacterial and antifungal activities against various bacterial and fungal strains.

Keywords : Schiff base, FAB mass, IR, UV-Vis, antibacterial, antifungal.

Introduction

Schiff bases and their metal complexes form an important class of compounds and find extensive application in different fields¹. The study of reactivity of Schiff bases containing heteroaromatics has received a great deal of attention in the coordination chemistry of transition, inner-transition and main group elements. Among them the enduring popularity of tridentate and tetradentate Schiff bases are due to their synthetic ease with which they are synthesised and their complexing ability. In recent years Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes have attracted greater interest in bioorganic, medicinal and pharmaceutical field²⁻⁴. Metal complexes of Schiff bases have been used for catalysis, molecular recognition and in biological process. Metal complexes of nitrogen and sulphur containing ligands have attracted considerable attention, because nitrogen and sulphur play key role, in many metallo biomolecules⁵. These type of Schiff bases show biological applications including antibacterial^{6,7}, antifun-

gal^{8,9} and antitumour activities^{10,11}. Here, in this communication, we describe the synthesis, characterization, antibacterial and antifungal studies of some trivalent transition metal complexes.

Results and discussion

Analytical and physical data of the ligand and its metal complexes are given in Table 1. The ligand and its metal complexes are coloured and stable in air. The analytical results obtained are in good agreement with the calculated values for the suggested formula. The ligand is soluble in common organic solvents, but the complexes are found to be soluble in DMSO and DMF. The molar conductance values in DMSO (Table 1) adequately support the 1 : 1 electrolytic nature of the metal complexes¹².

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectrum of the free ligand has been compared with the spectra of complexes in order to determine the coordination sites that may involved in chelation. The

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of ligand and its metal complexes

Compd.	Yield (%)	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Molar conductance ^a ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
			C	H	N	S	M	
HNTA	80	Yellow	62.16 (62.32)	3.83 (3.92)	6.06 (6.13)	13.73 (13.86)	-	-
[Mn(NTA) ₂]OAc	67	Brown	53.21 (53.38)	3.25 (3.40)	5.03 (4.98)	11.34 (11.40)	9.76 (9.87)	52.78
[Fe(NTA) ₂]Cl	72	Dark brown	52.18 (52.24)	2.87 (2.92)	5.08 (5.13)	11.51 (11.62)	10.12 (10.15)	53.45
[Co(NTA) ₂]NO ₃	69	Blue	49.43 (49.57)	2.81 (2.77)	7.22 (7.23)	11.03 (11.07)	10.13 (10.22)	52.32

^aMeasured in DMSO.

position and intensity of the peaks are expected to change upon chelation. The IR spectrum of the ligand shows a characteristic peak at 1607 cm^{-1} is due to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ of the azomethine group. On complexation, this peak has been shifted to lower frequency region by about $\sim 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the involvement of azomethine nitrogen atom in coordination with the metal ion¹³. The asymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies of the carboxylate (COO^-) group are observed at 1589 and 1292 cm^{-1} in free ligand. But in the complexes, these bands have been shifted to the region of about 1576 – 1571 and 1311 – 1319 cm^{-1} respectively indicating the coordination of carboxylate oxygen atom to the metal ion. In all case the difference between asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylate group¹⁴ is $> 220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This indicates monodentate bonding mode of the carboxylate group in the complexes. The band at 846 cm^{-1} corresponds to the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C})$ group of thiophene moiety in the ligand, is shifted to higher frequency region at 856 – 869 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicate the participation of thiophene sulphur atom in coordination¹⁵. The bonding of the ligand to the metal ion is further supported by the appearance of new bands in the region 521 – 528 , 470 – 476 and 388 – 395 cm^{-1} have been assigned to the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ bands respectively in the far IR spectra of the metal complexes^{15,18}. These observations reveal that the ligand binds the metal ion in a tridentate manner and coordinating through azomethine nitrogen, carboxylate oxygen and thiophene ring sulphur atom.

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligand and its cobalt(III) complex recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ solution are shown in Fig. 1(a) and (b). The ¹H NMR peak assignments are given in Table 2. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand shows a signal appearing at 8.12 ppm has been assigned to the hydrogen of the azomethine moiety and it has been shifted to 7.96 ppm in the cobalt(III) complex is the clear indication of participation of $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ in complex formation. Signals for aromatic protons and thiophene protons of the ligand is observed in the range of 6.48 – 7.91 ppm are shifted to lower region of 6.24 – 7.78 ppm in the complex indicating the participation of thiophene sulphur in complex formation¹⁵. Also in the ligand spectrum, a peak at 9.95 ppm has been assigned for the carboxylic proton and is completely disappear in the complex indicating the involvement of carboxylic group in the complex formation with deprotonation¹⁵.

FAB mass spectra :

The FAB mass spectrum of the ligand shows a well-defined molecular ion peak at m/z 231 (Relative intensity = 34%). This is consistent with the proposed molecular formulae of the ligand. The spectrum of ligand shows base peak at 186 (Relative intensity = 100%) shows the removal of carboxylic group from the ligand during fragmentation. The FAB mass spectrum of cobalt(III) complex shows a peak at m/z 581 (Relative intensity = 17%) corresponding to its molecular weight. The mass spectrum of the complex indicates that the metal to ligand ratio to be 1 : 2 in the complex.

Fig. 1. Proton NMR spectrum of (a) ligand and (b) cobalt(III) complex.

Electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements :

The absorption spectra of the ligand and its complexes are measured in DMSO solution. The ligand spectrum shows sharp bands at 214, 216 and 286 nm and a shoulder band at 320 nm. These bands can be attributed to

$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of the ligand¹⁵. These bands are marginally red shifted in the spectra of the metal complexes, which show that no structural alteration of the ligand occurred on chelation.

In an octahedral field, 5D term of manganese(III) with d^4 configuration splits into $^5E_{2g}$ and $^5T_{2g}$ and only one

Table 2. ^1H NMR spectra of the ligand and its cobalt(III) complex

Compd.	Chemical shift	Assignment
Ligand	9.95	Single hydrogen of carboxylic group
	6.48–8.12	Eight hydrogen multiplet (4 ArH, 1 azomethine, 3 thiophene H)
	2.50	Solvent peak
Cobalt(III) complex	6.24–7.96	Multiplet of 16 H (8 ArH, 2 azomethine, 6 thiophene H)
	2.50	Solvent peak

$d-d$ transition is expected i.e. $^5E_{2g} \rightarrow ^5T_{2g}$. However, the high-spin octahedral manganese(III) complexes are susceptible to Jahn-Teller distortion and hence involved the split components of $^5E_{2g}$ and $^5T_{2g}$ in low symmetry. Here a broad band at ~ 549 nm and a weak shoulder at 472 nm are observed. This can be due to the transition resulting from the lowering of symmetry from octahedral^{19,20}. Although the orbital angular momentum is expected to be quenched, its contribution to magnetic moment is not completely eliminated because of the spin-orbit coupling and the magnetic moment calculated for an octahedral complex is about 4.8 B.M. In the present case, magnetic moment is only slightly lower than the spin only value expected for high-spin octahedral manganese(III) complexes and the value observed (4.74 B.M.) is comparable with those reported for similar type of manganese(III) complexes²¹. This value also suggests the absence of any appreciable metal-metal interaction in the complexes. On the basis of these observations, a distorted octahedral geometry has been proposed for manganese(III) complex.

For iron(III) complex, all the electronic transitions are spin forbidden as well as Laporte forbidden, so that the ligand field bands in the spectrum of iron(III) complex are weak. These weak bands are often masked by charge transfer bands and it is difficult to have any structural correlation from spectral data^{22,23}. The magnetic moment value obtained for iron(III) complex (5.78 B.M.) is in favour to infer the presence of an octahedral geometry. The reduction in spin only value is often caused by anti-ferromagnetic interaction or due to the presence of high-spin and low-spin equilibrium²⁴. From this magnetic mo-

ment data an octahedral geometry has been presumed and there is no metal-metal interaction.

Trivalent cobalt(III) usually gives six coordinated complexes involving d^2sp^3 hybridization having octahedral structure and most of them are diamagnetic. Here also the cobalt(III) complex has been found to be diamagnetic. The cobalt(III) complex exhibit a strong band at 584 nm with a shoulder at 484 nm, arising from $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ transitions respectively. The transition together with diamagnetic nature of cobalt(III) complex suggest six coordinated octahedral geometry²⁰.

On the basis of the above spectral, physicochemical and analytical data the proposed structure for the ligand and its metal complexes are given in Fig. 2(a) and (b).

Fig. 2. Proposed structure of (a) ligand and (b) metal complexes.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

The thermogram of iron(III) complex (Fig. 3) indicates three stages decomposition. The first stage of de-

Fig. 3. TG-DTG curve of iron(III) complex.

composition starts at 200 °C and completed at 280 °C shows a DTG peak temperature at 276 °C with a mass loss of 13.06% (calcd. 15.24%). The second stage of decomposition take place in the temperature range 300–410 °C with a DTG peak at 356 °C and the mass loss is 41.83% (calcd. 41.71%). The third stage of decomposition in the range 450–510 °C follows a mass loss of 71.01% (calcd. 73.29%) with a DTG peak temperature at 492 °C and is reliable with the oxidative decomposition of the complex, leading to the formation of metal oxide.

Kinetic data :

The kinetic parameters such as the activation energy E , the pre-exponential factor A and order for each stages of decomposition are calculated employing the Coats-Redfern equation²⁵. The value of $\log g(\alpha)/T^2$ versus $1/T \times 10^3$ plots gives a straight line where slope and intercept are used for calculating kinetic parameters (Table 3). There was no definite trend in the values of the entropy of activation. But the negative value of the entropy of activation in the present case indicated that the activated complex has a more ordered structure than the reactants^{26,27}.

Powder X-ray diffraction : The X-ray diffraction pattern of the ligand (Fig. 4a) indicates its high crystallinity. The diffractogram shows 16 reflections for 2θ value ranging from 13° to 45° with maxima at $2\theta = 12.8890^\circ$, which corresponds to interplanar distance $d = 6.8627 \text{ \AA}$. The main peaks have been indexed using the XRDA software and the data obtained are tabulated in Table 4. The observed $\sin^2\theta$ value and 2θ values obtained have been compared with the calculated values²⁸. A comparison of these values shows good agreement between observed and calculated values. Hence the ligand is successfully indexed to orthorhombic crystal systems with the lattice constant unit cell parameters are; $a = 9.5307 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 7.844 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 8.3416 \text{ \AA}$. The unit cell volume is found to be 623.61 \AA^3 .

The cobalt(III) complex (Fig. 4b) indicates 14 reflections in X-ray diffractogram which is between the 2θ values ranging from 12° to 40° with 2θ maxima at 12.218° which corresponds to d value of 7.2376 \AA . The complex shows sharp crystalline peaks and its data given in Table 5. Here also the comparison of the observed and calculated $\sin^2\theta$ value and 2θ values of the ligand as well

Table 3. Kinetics parameters data of the iron(III) complex

Decomposition stages	Order (<i>n</i>)	Correlation coefficient	Energy of activation ($E_a/kJ\ mol^{-1}$)	Arrhenius factor (A/s^{-1})	Entropy of activation ($\Delta S^\ddagger/kJ\ K^{-1}\ mol^{-1}$)
I	2.5	0.99965	156.23	2.6018×10^{13}	6.8809
II	2	0.9985	137.94	3.0153×10^{11}	-31.794
III	2	0.99965	147.91	3.33×10^{12}	-68.218

Fig. 4. XRD patterns of (a) ligand and (b) cobalt(III) complex.

Table 4. Powder XRD data of the ligand

<i>d</i> -spacing	Calcd. (2 θ)	Obsd. (2 θ)	Obsd. (Sin ² θ)	Calcd. (Sin ² θ)	<i>hkl</i>
6.3739	14.6129	13.8821	0.0145	0.0161	110
4.4114	18.6040	20.5765	0.0318	0.0261	200
4.1125	21.4570	21.5905	0.0350	0.0346	201
4.0322	21.8039	22.0255	0.0364	0.0357	210
3.4246	24.5225	24.8848	0.0463	0.0451	120
3.0355	25.9157	25.9966	0.0505	0.0502	112
3.1672	26.7798	28.1514	0.0590	0.0536	121
3.0355	29.4706	29.3993	0.0643	0.0647	220
2.8922	31.3996	30.8911	0.0708	0.0732	221
2.7486	32.6922	32.5494	0.0784	0.0792	122
2.6756	33.5448	33.4632	0.0828	0.0832	103
2.6013	34.1844	34.4476	0.0875	0.0863	013
2.4568	36.6408	36.5432	0.0982	0.0988	222
2.3444	37.4142	38.3620	0.1078	0.1028	203
2.1998	40.8594	40.9941	0.1224	0.1218	123
2.0132	44.1824	44.9897	0.1462	0.1414	223

Table 5. Powder XRD data of cobalt(III) complex

<i>d</i> -spacing	Calcd. (2 θ)	Obsd. (2 θ)	Obsd. (Sin ² θ)	Calcd. (Sin ² θ)	<i>hkl</i>
7.2376	12.4841	12.2187	0.0113	0.0118	110
6.5841	12.7878	13.4369	0.0136	0.0124	011
5.6186	15.8192	15.7592	0.0187	0.0189	111
4.6176	19.1546	19.2049	0.0278	0.0276	120
3.8862	22.6440	22.8643	0.0392	0.0385	211
3.8176	23.1568	23.2806	0.0406	0.0402	112
3.4561	25.1180	25.7558	0.0496	0.0472	220
3.3057	26.9762	26.9488	0.0542	0.0544	221
3.1453	27.4128	28.3512	0.0599	0.0561	121
3.0646	29.3174	29.1136	0.0631	0.0640	003
2.8362	30.8000	31.5174	0.0736	0.0705	103
2.6210	34.9500	34.1812	0.0862	0.0901	203
2.4781	35.9960	36.2181	0.0965	0.0954	213
2.3010	38.9800	39.1158	0.1119	0.1113	223

as the complex are in good agreement. Therefore orthorhombic crystal system can be assigned for the complex with lattice parameter; $a = 9.5285 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 10.5936 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 9.1312 \text{ \AA}$ and unit cell volume is found to be 921.72 \AA^3 .

In vitro biological activity :

The ligand and its metal complexes were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities and the results shown in Table 6. The results (Fig. 5) show that the tested compounds show remarkable biological activities against different types of bacteria (*S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*) and fungi (*A. flavus* and *A. niger*). The bacterial studies infer that metal chelates are more active against bacterial strains than the free ligand. The bacterial activity follows the order : $[\text{Co}(\text{NTA})_2]\text{NO}_3 > [\text{Fe}(\text{NTA})_2]\text{Cl} > [\text{Mn}(\text{NTA})_2]\text{OAc} > \text{HNTA}$. The higher activity of metal complexes compared to ligand may be due to the change in the reactivity of ligand after coordination²⁹. Furthermore coordination reduces the polarity of the metal ion mainly because of partial sharing of its positive charge with donor group within the chelate ring system. This process, in turn, increases the lipophilic nature of the central metal atom, which favours its permeation more efficiently through the lipid layer of microorganisms. The action of compound may also involve the formation of hydrogen bond through the azomethine group with the active centre of cell constituents, resulting in interference with normal cell process. The ligand and the complexes show higher activities against both the fungi. Here also the enhanced antifungal activity of complexes can be explained by chelation theory³⁰. The MIC values (Table 7) of all the compounds were studied against the bacteria and fungi. The MIC of $[\text{Co}(\text{NTA})_2]\text{NO}_3$, which

Table 6. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of ligand and its metal complexes

Compd.	Inhibition zone diameter (mm)					
	Bacteria				Fungi	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
HNTA	15	14	13	15	14	15
$[\text{Mn}(\text{NTA})_2]\text{OAc}$	23	21	17	20	17	20
$[\text{Fe}(\text{NTA})_2]\text{Cl}$	26	25	19	21	19	21
$[\text{Co}(\text{NTA})_2]\text{NO}_3$	28	27	22	24	21	24
Streptomycin	30	32	32	34	-	-
Fluconazole	-	-	-	-	27	31

Fig. 5. The scheme of diagram for antibacterial and antifungal activities of ligand and its metal complex.

Table 7. Minimum inhibitory concentration results of ligand and its metal complexes in $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Compd.	Minimum Inhibition Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)					
	Bacteria				Fungi	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
HNTA	40	35	40	40	50	50
[Mn(NTA) ₂]OAc	15	20	20	25	20	25
[Fe(NTA) ₂]Cl	15	20	15	15	20	15
[Co(NTA) ₂]NO ₃	10	10	10	10	15	15
Streptomycin	5	5	5	5	-	-
Fluconazole	-	-	-	-	15	15

show higher antibacterial and antifungal activities are found to be 10 and 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively.

Generally the antimicrobial property increased on chelation. However we could not make a distinct mechanism. Actually antimicrobial activity cannot be explained on the basis of a single factor such as electronegativity. Thus it can be concluded that the antimicrobial properties

has been a combination of several factors such as nature of ligand, nature of metal ion, steric, electronic and pharmacokinetic factors.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. Thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde, 2-aminobenzoic acid and

ferric chloride were purchased from Merck. Solvents used for spectroscopic studies were purified by standard procedures³¹. Manganese(III) acetate was prepared according to reported procedure. Elemental analysis (C, H, N) was carried out on elemental analyzer system Elementar Vario EL 111 Carlo Erba 1108 Analyzer. The metal contents of the complexes were determined using a Nulab GBC 902 Atomic Absorption Spectrometer in an acetylene/air flame. Molar conductance measurements were carried out in DMSO using a Systronics Model 304 digital conductivity meter. Infrared spectra of the ligand and its metal complexes were measured using KBr disc with a Jasco FT/IR 300 E-Fourier Transform Infrared spectrophotometer covering the range 400–4000 cm^{-1} and the far IR spectra in 100–500 cm^{-1} region using CSI disc on a polytec FIR-30 Fourier transform far-infrared spectrometer. Electronic absorption spectra were measured on a Shimadzu UV 2100 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. FAB mass spectra of ligand and its cobalt(III) complex were recorded on (JMS SX-102) Jeol mass spectrometer/data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as FAB gas. Magnetic measurements of the complexes were performed on a Magway MSB Mkl Magnetic susceptibility balance at room temperature. Proton NMR spectra of the ligand and its cobalt(III) complex were recorded on a Jeol GSX 400 MHz FT NMR spectrometer employing TMS as internal reference. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out using a thermobalance of the type Mettler Toledo System in dynamic air, at a heating rate 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Powder X-ray diffraction were carried out on a Siemens D 5000 model spectrometer.

Preparation of Schiff base :

The Schiff base was prepared by the condensation of methanolic solution (25 ml) of thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde (10 mmol) with 2-aminobenzoic acid (10 mmol) in methanol (50 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h and then concentrated. The yellow solid product formed was separated by filtration, washed successively with ethanol, ether and dried in vacuum over P_2O_5 . The Schiff base was further purified by recrystallisation from methanol.

Preparation of manganese(III) and iron(III) complexes :

The complexes were prepared by adding a methanolic solution (25 ml) of manganese(III) acetate/iron(III) chlo-

ride (5 mmol) to a hot methanolic solution (25 ml) of the ligand (10 mmol) in small portions. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 6.5–7.0 and refluxed for about 3 h. On cooling, the complex separated was filtered, washed successively with ethanol, ether and finally dried in vacuum over P_2O_5 .

Preparation of cobalt(III) complex :

Cobalt(III) complex was synthesized using $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CO}_3]\text{NO}_3 \cdot 1/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as synthetic intermediate, which was prepared according to a reported procedure³². To a hot methanolic solution (50 ml) of the carbonate complex (5 mmol), ligand (10 mmol) dissolved in methanol (25 ml) was added in small portions. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 4–5 and refluxed for 4 h. The solution was filtered and concentrated over a water-bath. On cooling, the complex separated was filtered, washed successively with alcohol, ether and finally dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum.

Antimicrobial activity :

The *in vitro* antibacterial activities of the investigated compounds were tested against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* (Gram-positive bacteria) and *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Gram-negative bacteria) by agar diffusion method using agar nutrient as the medium. The discs were placed on the already, seeded plates and incubated at 35 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 h. The diameter (mm) of the inhibition zone around each disc was measured after 24 h. The antifungal activity was evaluated by the disc diffusion method against the fungi *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus niger*, cultured on potato dextrose agar as medium. The fungicidal activity of the compounds was measured after 72 h. Streptomycin and fluconazole were used as standards for antibacterial and antifungal studies respectively. The MIC is the lowest concentration, which exhibited the same turbidity as the blank tube and the MIC was determined by serial dilution technique³³. The stock solution (10^{-2} M) was prepared by dissolving the compound in DMSO and the solutions were diluted to different concentration in the same solvent in order to find the MIC values.

Conclusion :

The manganese(III), iron(III) and cobalt(III) complexes with a ONS ligand, derived from thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde and 2-aminobenzoic acid, were synthesized. A comparative study of their physicochemical properties has

been made through elemental analysis, molar conductance, IR, electronic spectra, magnetic moment. The conductance data indicate that all the complexes are 1 : 1 electrolytes. The IR data reveal that the Schiff base ligand coordinates through the azomethine nitrogen, thiophene sulphur and carboxylate oxygen atoms. From the analytical and spectral data a distorted octahedral geometry for manganese(III) complex and six-coordinated octahedral geometry for iron(III) and cobalt(III) complexes have been assigned. The thermal decomposition of the iron(III) complex is found to be a three-stage process. Powder XRD results show that the ligand and its cobalt(III) complex are of crystalline nature. Antimicrobial activities indicate that the cobalt(III) complex has higher activity compared to other compounds may also be due to high biological activity nature of cobalt metal. The antimicrobial activity follows the order : $[\text{Co}(\text{NTA})_2]\text{NO}_3 > [\text{Fe}(\text{NTA})_2]\text{Cl} > [\text{Mn}(\text{NTA})_2]\text{OAc} > \text{HNTA}$.

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References

1. P. A. Vigato and S. Tamburini, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **248**, 717.
2. N. V. Kulkarni, M. P. Sathisha, S. Budagumpi, G. S. Kurdekar and V. K. Revankar, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2010, **63**, 1451.
3. P. Roy, K. Dhara, M. Manassero and P. Banerjee, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2008, **11**, 265.
4. J. Chakraborty, M. Nandi, H. Mayer-Figge, W. S. Sheldrick, L. Sorace, A. Bhaumik and P. Banerjee, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **32**, 5033.
5. O. A. M. Ali, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2007, **60**, 1213.
6. A. A. A. Abu-Hussen, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2006, **59**, 157.
7. M. S. Karthikeyan, D. J. Prasad, B. Poojary, K. S. Bhat, B. S. Holla and N. S. Kumari, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2006, **14**, 7482.
8. K. Singh, M. S. Barwa and P. Tyagi, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2006, **41**, 1.
9. P. Panneerselvam, R. R. Nair, G. Vijayalakshmi, E. H. Subramanian and S. K. Sridhar, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **40**, 225.
10. S. N. Pandeya, D. Sriram, G. Nath and E. Declercq, *Eur. J. Pharmacol.*, 1999, **9**, 25.
11. O. M. Walsh, M. J. Meegan, R. M. Prendergast and T. A. Nakib, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1996, **31**, 989.
12. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
13. J. M. Seco, M. Quiros and M. J. G. Garmendia, *Polyhedron*, 2000, **19**, 1005.
14. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 6th ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New Jersey, 2009.
15. R. Mladenova, M. Ignatova, N. Manolova, T. Petrova and I. Rashkov, *Eur. Polym. J.*, 2002, **38**, 989.
16. G. G. Mohamed, M. M. Omar and A. H. H. Hindy, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2005, **62**, 1140.
17. A. Z. El-Sonbati, A. S. Al-Shihri and A. A. El-Bindary, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 1763.
18. S. A. Patil, V. H. Naik, A. D. Kulkarni and P. S. Badami, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2010, **75**, 347.
19. K. Mohanan, *Orient. J. Chem.*, 2004, **20**, 331.
20. V. P. Daniel and K. Mohanan, *Orient. J. Chem.*, 2006, **22**, 603.
21. S. Iffet, G. Necla and G. Turgut, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2001, **31**, 1175.
22. S. Sarkar and K. Dey, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2005, **62**, 383.
23. L. A. Saghatforoush, A. Aminkhani and F. Chalabian, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2009, **34**, 899.
24. B. Murukan and K. Mohanan, *J. Enzym Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **22**, 65.
25. A. W. Coats and J. P. Redfern, *Nature*, 1964, **20**, 68.
26. K. K. Aravindakshan and K. Muraleedharan, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1989, **155**, 247.
27. M. Thankamony, B. S. Kumari, G. Rijulal and K. Mohanan, *J. Rare Earths*, 2008, **26**, 463.
28. S. A. Patil, S. N. Unki, A. D. Kulkarni, V. H. Naik and P. S. Badami, *J. Mol. Str.*, 2011, **985**, 330.
29. Z. H. Chohan, A. Scozzafava and C. T. Supuran, *J. Enzyme Inhib. Chem.*, 2003, **18**, 259.
30. K. Mohanan and S. N. Devi, *Russian J. Coord. Chem.*, 2006, **32**, 600.
31. D. D. Perrin, W. L. Armarego and D. R. Perrin, "Purification of Laboratory Chemicals", 2nd ed., Pergamon, Oxford, UK, 1980.
32. J. C. Bailor (Jr.), "Inorganic Synthesis", McGraw Hill, New York, 1953.
33. S. Jain, R. Sharma, V. Jain, R. Jat, C. Dubey and S. Bhardwaj, *J. Pharm. Res.*, 2010, **3**, 274.